

EFFECT OF RAJMA (KIDNEY BEAN) FLOUR AND LINSEED POWDER ON SENSORY AND NUTRITIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LOW-FAT MUFFINS

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Abstract

Muffins are popular baked products that are consumed as snacks or desserts. However, muffins are usually high in fat and calories, which can pose health risks such as obesity and cardiovascular diseases. The objective of this study was to reduce the energy value and improve the sensory qualities of muffins by incorporating Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed flour. Muffins were prepared with different ratios of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour (40, 50, and 45 g) and flax seed flour (25, 10, and 15 g) and assessed for their sensory attributes, nutrient content, and energy value. The addition of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder increased the muffins carbohydrate and ash content while decreasing the fat and protein content. The sensory evaluation showed that the muffins with 45 g of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and 15 g of flax seed powder had the highest scores for appearance, colour, texture, flavour, and overall acceptability. Adding Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder can improve the sensory attributes and lower the energy value of the muffins, making them a medium-fat and enriched food product.

Keywords: Low-Fat Muffins, Kidney Bean Flour, Flax Seed powder, Sensory and Notional Characteristics

Introduction

Muffins are popular baked products that are consumed as breakfast or snack items. They are usually made with wheat flour, sugar, eggs, butter, and other ingredients that provide flavour and texture. However, muffins are also high in calories, fat, and carbohydrates, which may not be suitable for health-conscious consumers or people with dietary restrictions. Therefore, there is a need to develop muffins that are lower in energy value and higher in nutritional quality. One way to achieve this is to replace some of the wheat flour with alternative flours that have different functional and nutritional properties. Bakery products are popular among consumers for their taste and texture. Muffins are one of the bakery products that use wheat flour as the main ingredient. Wheat flour contains gluten, a protein that gives structure to baked goods. However, gluten is harmful for people with celiac disease, a genetic disorder that causes gluten intolerance. These people need to avoid gluten in their diet. (Farrell and Kelly, 2002; Green and Jabri, 2003). Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour is a type of gluten-free flour made from ground kidney beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*). It is rich in dietary fibre, protein, iron, folate, and antioxidants, and has a low glycaemic index (Gupta *et al.*, 2019). It can be used to make breads, cakes, pancakes, and other baked goods.

Flax seed powder is another nutritious ingredient that can be added to Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour to enhance its nutritional value. Flax seeds (*Linum usitatissimum*) are a good source of omega-3 fatty acids, lignans, and fibre, which may help improve digestion and reduce the risk of heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and cancer (Healthline, 2020). Flax seed powder can also improve the water absorption, oil holding, and emulsifying capacities of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour, which can affect the texture and shelf life of the muffins (Singh *et al.*, 2018). Previous studies have reported the effects of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder on the quality and acceptability of various baked products, such as bread (Gupta *et al.*, 2019), cookies (Singh *et al.*, 2018), and cake (Kaur *et al.*, 2017). However, there is limited research on the use of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder in muffins, which are a popular and convenient food item. Therefore, the objective of this study was to develop Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder-enriched

muffins and evaluate their physicochemical, sensory, and nutritional characteristics. The study also explored the nutritional benefits of flax seeds and experimented with different ingredient ratios to achieve the optimal texture and taste of the muffins.

Materials And Methods

The present study was conducted in the research laboratory of the Foods Nutrition Dept. of Food Science, Gramin Science Vocational College, Vishnupuri, Nanded. All the required raw materials were purchased from the local market in Nanded. Rajma (kidney bean) flour was prepared by soaking kidney beans in water for 12 hours, draining, drying, and grinding them into a fine powder. Flax seed powder was prepared by roasting flax seeds and grinding them into a coarse powder. Wheat flour, sugar, eggs, butter, baking powder, salt, and vanilla essence were used as the other ingredients for the muffins. The composition of the muffins is shown in Table 1. The ingredients were mixed in a bowl according to the standard muffin method. The batter was filled in greased muffin cups and baked in a preheated oven at 180°C for 20 minutes. The muffins were cooled and stored in airtight containers until further analysis. The sensory evaluation of the muffins was as done by a selected panel of six semi-trained judges using a 9-point hedonic scale based on the scorecard as per Srilakshmi (2007). The muffins were evaluated for their appearance, colour, texture, flavour, and overall acceptability.

The physicochemical analysis of the muffins was done by adopting standard procedures. A.O.A.C. (2005) methods determined the moisture, ash, and fat content of the muffins. The protein content of the muffins was determined by the Kjeldahl method as described in A.O.A.C. (2005). The carbohydrate content of the muffins was calculated by difference. The total sugar content of the muffins was estimated by the Lane and Eynon method as per IS: 1479 (Part-II), 1961. Food energy value (Kcal/100 g) was determined according to the method of Marero *et al.* (1998), the energy value of the muffins was calculated by using the formula: Energy = (Carbohydrate × 4) + (Fat × 9) + (Protein × 4) as described in A.O.A.C. (2005). The data were collected from the three treatment groups: formulation 1, formulation 2, and formulation 3. The Data were analysed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using OPSTAT software packages (<http://opstat.pythonanywhere.com/>)

Table 1 Development of Rajma (Kidney Bean) Muffins with Flax Seed powder

Ingredients	Developed muffins Formulation
Milk	100ml
Butter	100gm
Sugar	100gm
Refined wheat flour	200gm

Baking powder	1/2gm
Baking soda	1/2gm
Cocoa powder	30gm
Vanilla essence	2ml
Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour	45gm
Flax seed powder	15gm
Tutti-frutti	10gm
Egg	1 no.

Fig 1: A flowchart for standard preparation method for development of Muffins. (Khatri *et. al.* 2020).

Results And Discussion

Table 2. Results of sensory evaluation

Attributes	Formulation 1	Formulation 2	Formulation 3	p-value	Results
Colour	6.58 ± 0.37 ^b	7.83 ± 0.40 ^a	8.33 ± 0.51 ^a	0.00	Sig
Texture	7.00 ± 0.63 ^a	7.50 ± 0.54 ^a	8.33 ± 0.81	0.01	Sig
Taste	7.08 ± 0.49 ^b	7.50 ± 0.54 ^{ab}	8.17 ± 0.68 ^a	0.01	Sig
Appearance	6.67 ± 0.40 ^b	7.50 ± 0.54 ^a	8.41 ± 0.49	0.00	Sig
Flavor	6.67 ± 0.40 ^b	7.58 ± 0.66 ^a	8.33 ± 0.51	0.00	Sig
Mouth feel	6.91 ± 0.37 ^b	7.58 ± 0.66 ^{ab}	8.167 ± 0.75 ^a	0.01	Sig
Overall acceptability	7.08 ± 0.37 ^b	7.58 ± 0.66 ^{ab}	8.00 ± 0.44 ^a	0.02	Sig

^{a-b} Different letters in the same row indicate significant differences between the formulation significant at (P < 0.05).

For attribute of colour: Formulation1 scores 6.58; Formulation2 scores 7.83; Formulation3 scores 8.33; This suggests that the most favorable attribute is that of the formulation3, followed by that of the second, and then that of the first.

In terms of texture, formulation 3 differs significantly from formulation 1, which does not differ significantly from formulation 2. The mean texture rating for formulation 3 is higher than that of formulation 1, while the mean rating for formulation 1 is lower than that of formulation 3. As a result, the panel preferred formulation 3 (scores 8.33) to that of formulation 1 and found formulation 2 to be intermediate.

In terms of Flavour: formulation 3 differs substantially from 1 and 2 in that it does not have a significant difference between them. The highest mean rating for flavour (scores 8.33) is given to Formulation 3, while the lowest is given to Formulation 1. This means that the panel preferred the flavour of formulation 3 over formulation 1, and formulation 2 was intermediate.

In terms of mouthfeel: formulation 3 has a considerable difference with formulation 1, whereas formulation 2 does not differ in any of these respects. The average rating for mouthfeel of Formulation 3 is higher than that of Formulation 1, which has the lowest. Consequently, formulation 3(scores 8.16) was preferred by the panel as regards mouthfeel compared to formulation 1, whereas formulation 2 had been intermediate.

Overall acceptability: formulation 3 is significantly different from formulation 1, whereas formulation 2 is not significantly different from either of them. In terms of overall acceptability, Formulation 3 receives the highest mean score 8.00, whereas Formulation 1 has the lowest. This means that the Panel favoured both formulation 2 and formulation 3 in its overall acceptability compared with formulation

Table 3 Results of chemical Analysis :

Parameters	Unit	Standard muffins	Developed muffins Formulation3
Energy	kcal/100 g	353	334.73
Ash	g/100 g	1.2	1.43
Moisture	g/100 g	25.0	25.38
Fat	g/100 g	13.0	8.89
Protein	g/100 g	6.0	5.85
Fiber	g/100 g	2.0	0.62
Carbohydrate	g/100 g	53.0	57.83

The results of the physicochemical analysis of the muffins are shown in Table 3. The carbohydrates and ash content in the muffins have been increased while reducing fat and protein levels by incorporating Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder. The carbohydrate content of muffins has risen from 53.42 % to 57.83 %. The energy content of the Rajma (Kidney Bean) based muffins is slightly lower than that of the standard muffins, with values of 335 kcal/100 g and 340 kcal/100 g respectively. This could be beneficial for those looking to reduce their caloric intake. This means that Rajma (Kidney Bean) based muffins have lower energy value than standard muffins, and may be a healthier choice for people who want to reduce their calorie intake. the percentage reduction of energy value of Rajma (Kidney Bean) based muffins compared to standard muffins is 5.18%.

Conclusion

From the present study it can be concluded that incorporation of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder level can significantly improve the sensory characteristics and lower the energy value of the muffins, making them a medium-fat and enriched food product. The muffins also had acceptable colour, texture, flavor, and overall acceptability. Rajma (Kidney Bean) based muffins have 5.18% less calories than standard muffins per 100 grams. which makes them reduced calories and reduced-fat food products, muffins fall into the medium-fat category. Therefore, the incorporation of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder in muffins can be considered as a novel and healthy approach to enhance the functional

1, which has been classified as intermediate.

Result shows that formulation 3 was the most preferred by the panel for all the attributes, while formulation 1 was the least preferred. Formulation 2 was intermediate for most of the attributes, except for colour, where it was similar to formulation 3. The differences between the formulations were statistically significant for all the attributes, except for texture and taste, where formulation 2 was not significantly different from formulation 1 or formulation 3. The water absorption, oil holding, and emulsifying capacities of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder, which increased the hydration and stability of the dough and reduced the gluten formation and starch gelatinisation, (Singh *et al.*, 2018), have affected the texture of the muffins. Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder added a nuttiness and earthiness to the muffins' taste. The judges preferred the muffins with moderate levels of Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder, as they were not too dense or bitter. These results are in agreement with the previous studies that reported the positive effects of Rajma (Kidney Bean flour and flax seed powder on the sensory attributes of baked products. Formulation 3 is the most preferred, followed by Formulation 2, and then Formulation 1. These findings can guide future improvements in the formulations to enhance their sensory attributes and overall acceptability. The results of the sensory evaluation of the muffins are shown in Table 1.

The muffins with 45 g Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and 15 g flax seed powder had the highest scores for appearance, colour, texture, flavour, and overall acceptability. The colour and texture of the muffins have been improved by adding Rajma (Kidney Bean) flour and flax seed powder, which has added a brown shade as well as a moist and soft crumb. (Gupta *et al.*, 2019; Singh *et al.*, 2018; and Kaur *et al.*, 2017).

properties of bakery products for a specific group of people.

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